

A citation graph based impact estimate not relying on definitions of research fields

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Abstract

It has become evident in recent years that citation network clustering based research field classifications are difficult to make reliable enough to be used as basis for citation count normalization. This means that there is need for novel approaches, perhaps entirely without classifications. In this work, estimating the citation impact of a publication is done by an indicator that is defined, in addition to publication years, only using the local upstream citation graph. This local graph is divided into (partly overlapping) subgraphs for which citations are counted. The rationale is that usually there is a reason for citing, and that reason might have influence also beyond the direct citations. In other words, these subgraphs are considered to be characterized by a reason to cite the studied publication and the citations to the subgraphs to be generated (partly and likely implicitly) by that same reason. The indicator itself is calculated as an expected value of the citation counts to the subgraphs converted into weights, quantifying information spread originating from the studied publication. This method was adapted for the citation graph context from an article studying the influence of all nodes in a network, applied there to epidemiology ([Lawyer, 2015]). Here predictions of the indicator were tested producing results supporting that the indicator catches relevant information. Namely, correlation and mutual information between indicator based orderings of a set of 914 publications at varying time intervals from the publication year 2016 were calculated. These results were compared with

*Not to be submitted.

32 results supporting the method are given. In section Conclusions, some possible ways
 33 to develop the model further are mentioned.

34 2 Method

35 Information spread from the studied publication (publ-0) through its local upstream
 36 citation graph is modelled by first dividing the graph into sets of three connected
 37 nodes. Each set consists of publ-0 and two other publications that either cite publ-0
 38 directly, or one cites directly and the other cites the one making the direct citation (a
 39 second step citation), see Figure 1. These subgraphs are called units and considered
 40 to represent a reason to cite publ-0.

Figure 1: Local citation graph generates a set of subgraphs, called here units. Each unit contains the node for the studied publication and two other from the local graph. Links are in the direction of the citation, as depicted by link arrows. Each unit represents two citations, either twice a direct citation to the studied publication (these counted twice, see text), or a direct and an indirect. Publ-0 is the lowest in the figure and would be root node in case links were in the direction of information flow, i.e., reversed direction. Citation impact is defined as an expected value of citation count weights over the units. For the local graph in the figure, count for each of the four units is 2 and the corresponding weight is $1/4$.

41 In addition to the two citation steps from publ-0, the model incorporates citation
 42 counts (cc_2) to publications in which the indirect, second step citations are made.
 43 The cc_2 are considered a link to the rest of the citation network, not primarily
 44 relating to the reason to cite publ-0. The expected citation impact ECI is calculated
 45 with the formula

$$ECI = k(cc_2) \frac{ECI_1}{ECI_0} \quad (1)$$

46 In Equation (1), factor $k(cc_2)$ models the strength of connection between the
 47 local graph and the rest of the network and has the functional form $k(cc_2) = 1 +$
 48 $\ln(1 + cc_2)/10$, where \ln is the natural logarithm. ECI_1 is the unnormalized impact
 49 value and is calculated by

$$ECI_1 = - \sum_{i=1}^n w_i * \ln(w_i) \quad (2)$$

50 The weight $w_i = \frac{d_i}{\sum_{i=1}^n d_i}$ gives the part of citations unit i has obtained (d_i) when
 51 compared to the sum of citations to all units. Presenting these $n = cc_0 * (cc_0 - 1) + cc_1$
 52 unit citation counts (cc_0 are direct and cc_1 second step citation counts) as a vector
 53 gives

$$\vec{d} = [d_1, \dots, d_{n_0}, d_{n_0+1}, \dots, d_n], \quad (3)$$

54 where the first $n_0 = cc_0 * (cc_0 - 1)$ entries are for units formed by two direct
 55 citations, unit 1 in Figure 1. These units are counted twice (just counting the pairs
 56 would be $cc_0 * (cc_0 - 1)/2$), see units 1 and 2 in Figure 1, which has the rationale
 57 that two direct citations can either have the same or each a different reason to cite
 58 publ-0. The last $n - n_0 = cc_1$ entries are for units that include the second citation
 59 step, units 3 and 4 in Figure 1. Each represents a reason to cite publ-0, mediated
 60 by the publication directly citing it.

61 In Equation (1), the normalizing factor ECI_0 , that is needed to produce compara-
 62 ble estimates, is calculated using Equation (2) but with the weights $w_{0,i}$ determined
 63 by unit citation counts $d_{0,i}$ as

$$\vec{d}_0 = [n, 1_2, \dots, 1_n] \rightarrow \bar{w}_0 = \frac{1}{2n - 1} [n, 1_2, \dots, 1_n], \quad (4)$$

64 where $1_i = 1$ for all i . This vector does not correspond to an actual graph but is
 65 used to define a reference level of expected impact for graphs with the same number
 66 of direct (cc_0) and second step citations (cc_1).

Figure 2: A directed local citation graph with 13 nodes for a publication of interest (node 0). Direct citation count cc_0 is 2 (nodes 1 and 11), second step citation count cc_1 is 6 (nodes 2-6,12) and citations to those citing those citing publ-0, cc_2 , is 6 (nodes 7-10, 12-13). Node 12 has two roles, as the source for both a second step and a third step citation.

67 Figure 2 further illustrates usage of the local citation graph. For this graph, the
 68 unit citation count vector $\bar{d} = [6, 6, 6, 5, 5, 8, 7, 1]$ has length $cc_0 * (cc_0 - 1) + cc_1 =$
 69 $2 * 1 + 6 = 8$. The first two entries are for direct citations from nodes 1 and 11,
 70 the corresponding count 6 equals the 6 second step citations from nodes 2-6 and
 71 12. If there were more than two direct citations cc_0 , the count $cc_0 - 2$ would be
 72 added to both of these first entries. Similarly would be done for other pairs of direct
 73 citations, which all have their unit-specific second step citation counts cc_1 . The rest
 74 of the entries are for units formed by two consecutive citations, like the count 7,
 75 which is for node combination 0 - 1 - 2. The last count (one), is for 0 - 11 - 12 and
 76 comes from that publication represented by node 1 is citing publ-0. In summary,
 77 one counts edges directed to nodes of a unit. Figure 2 was made with the graph tool
 78 Gephi ([Bastian et al., 2009]).

79 The citation impact estimate for a publication that has generated the local
 80 graph in Figure 2 would, based on Equation (1), be $1.195 * \frac{1.998}{1.599} = 1.493$. For the
 81 calculation one needs $\bar{w} = \frac{\bar{d}}{\sum_{i=1}^n d_i} = \frac{\bar{d}}{44}$ and $cc_2 = 6$.

82 As stated in Introduction, the more dispersed the citations are, the higher the
 83 calculated impact. This can be exemplified by moving the link $9 \rightarrow 6$ to be $9 \rightarrow 12$,
 84 which only changes the distribution in \bar{d} , to $[6, 6, 6, 5, 5, 7, 7, 2]$, and therefore changes

85 only ECI_1 . Distribution in \bar{d} is then closer to uniform and produces a slightly higher
86 impact estimate 1.521.

87 3 Data and Numerical Results

88 Citation impact estimates for a set of 914 University of Helsinki (UH) publications
89 from 2016 were calculated using data from OpenCitations ([Peroni et al., 2020]).
90 The estimates were determined using lengthening time intervals of accumulating
91 citations, and the obtained series of impact estimate vectors were rank correlated.
92 Then the publications were partitioned into deciles and centiles, based on the impact
93 estimates, and the measure mutual information (MI) was calculated using these
94 quantile partitions. The correlations and the measure of dependence MI results
95 were compared to corresponding ones that were based on direct citation counts.
96 The latter are known to reasonably predict the following direct citation counts. This
97 comparison indicated that the rankings based on ECI, calculated using Equation (1),
98 are more stable over time and mainly higher also, especially when the time interval
99 between rankings is longer (which means 4-6 years in this study).

100 This method utilizes the second and third citation steps and therefore the delay
101 in the accumulation of these is of interest. On the level of the publication set (914
102 UH 2016 publications), second step cc_1 starts accumulating shortly after the first
103 direct citations and twice exceed cc_0 in 2017. As a sidenote, if there is considered
104 to be feedback $cc_0 = cc_0(cc_1) = const * cc_1$, then the growth of cc_1 is exponential, at
105 least during some period of time, though the constant may be small.

106 The citation impact ECI is proportional to a sum of random variates, (imagined
107 to be) generated from closely related distributions. These are power laws, or modi-
108 fied power laws ([Nuermaiti et al., 2021]), part of which are shifted one citation
109 count or two counts. Due to central limit theorem the ECI values can therefore
110 be expected to approximately follow a normal distribution, which is demonstrated
111 in Figure 3 for the 914 UH 2016 publications after one to six years of gathering
112 citations. This set, used here for numerical results, was compiled by excluding those
113 publ-0 that had less than three links in their local graphs by 2018. Publications in
114 the excluded group produce unit citation counts of zero and need to be handled by
115 giving them some base ECI value, not considered in this work. Direct citation count
116 distributions corresponding the ECI values in Figure 3 are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 3: Distribution of the impact indicator ECI as it develops using increasing time intervals from the publication year of the set (2016). The continuous line depicts normal distribution, with mean and standard deviation from the sample, to show the approximate normality of ECI.

Figure 4: Distribution of the citation count OCC as it develops in increasing time intervals from the publication year of the set 2016. The typical power law, or generalized power law, shape can be seen in the histograms.

117 **3.1 Numerical comparisons**

118 Calculated mutual information values are tabulated in Tables 1 and 2, and rank
 119 correlations can be found in Tables 3 and 4. They show that ECI predicts on
 120 average at least as well as OCC, and notably declines slower when time interval
 121 between rankings becomes longer. Both ECI and OCC are based on the same
 122 dataset.

Citations latest	MI_{decile} (ECI)	MI_{decile} (OCC)
2017 and 2018	1.11	1.10
2017 and 2019	0.87	0.82
2017 and 2020	0.77	0.70
2017 and 2021	0.72	0.63
2017 and 2022	0.71	0.61
2018 and 2019	1.83	1.65
2018 and 2020	1.54	1.35
2018 and 2021	1.41	1.18
2018 and 2022	1.37	1.13
2019 and 2020	2.18	1.94
2019 and 2021	1.98	1.62
2019 and 2022	1.91	1.55
2020 and 2021	2.51	2.11
2020 and 2022	2.39	1.95
2021 and 2022	2.91	2.49

Table 1: Comparing publication rankings based either on citation impact (ECI) or citation count (OCC). For both, mutual information MI (in shannons) between labelings of the publication set into deciles at varied time steps were calculated. I.e., it was compared how well ranking based on local citation graphs and citation counts, accumulated until the end of, for example, 2017 predict ranking based on accumulation until the end of 2018, 2019 and so on. The MI measures how much one can tell about one distribution based on the other, therefore higher MI is indicative of that the earlier ranking predicts better the later ranking. For reference, the maximal mutual information is here at about 3.32 ($\approx \log_2(10)$). It can be noted that MI_{decile} (ECI) are higher and decrease slower than MI_{decile} (OCC).

Citations latest	$MI_{centile}$ (ECI)	$MI_{centile}$ (OCC)
2017 and 2018	3.61	4.07
2017 and 2019	3.53	3.86
2017 and 2020	3.50	3.83
2017 and 2021	3.51	3.78
2017 and 2022	3.54	3.80
2018 and 2019	3.88	4.18
2018 and 2020	3.75	3.95
2018 and 2021	3.76	3.86
2018 and 2022	3.72	3.82
2019 and 2020	4.07	4.23
2019 and 2021	3.95	3.99
2019 and 2022	3.91	3.88
2020 and 2021	4.39	4.32
2020 and 2022	4.20	4.10
2021 and 2022	4.97	4.57

Table 2: Comparing publication rankins based either on citation impact (ECI) or citation count (OCC). For both, mutual information MI (in shannons) between labelings of the publication set into centiles at varied time steps were calculated. More details on interpretation can be found in caption of Table 1. For reference, the maximal mutual information is here at about 6.64 ($\approx \log_2(100)$). It can be noted that though $MI_{centile}$ (OCC) has higher values (except the last four), $MI_{centile}$ (ECI) decreases slower with lengthening time intervals between rankings than does $MI_{centile}$ (OCC).

ECI	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
2017	1	0.872	0.813	0.780	0.764	0.761
2018	0.872	1	0.971	0.946	0.934	0.930
2019	0.813	0.971	1	0.986	0.978	0.975
2020	0.780	0.946	0.986	1	0.996	0.994
2021	0.764	0.934	0.978	0.996	1	0.999
2022	0.761	0.930	0.975	0.994	0.999	1

OCC	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
2017	1	0.873	0.814	0.774	0.744	0.734
2018	0.873	1	0.955	0.927	0.904	0.894
2019	0.814	0.955	1	0.977	0.957	0.949
2020	0.774	0.927	0.977	1	0.985	0.978
2021	0.744	0.904	0.957	0.985	1	0.995
2022	0.734	0.894	0.949	0.978	0.995	1

Table 3: Spearman rank correlations for citation impact values ECI (upper table) and citation counts OCC (lower table). Tables show that correlation coefficients are mainly higher (13 out of 15) for ECI than for OCC, especially when time interval between rankings is longer. I.e., ECI based correlations are more stable as well.

ECI	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
2017	1	0.697	0.627	0.590	0.573	0.570
2018	0.697	1	0.857	0.804	0.782	0.776
2019	0.627	0.857	1	0.910	0.881	0.873
2020	0.590	0.804	0.910	1	0.952	0.939
2021	0.573	0.782	0.881	0.952	1	0.976
2022	0.570	0.776	0.873	0.939	0.976	1

OCC	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
2017	1	0.746	0.667	0.617	0.586	0.575
2018	0.746	1	0.856	0.797	0.758	0.742
2019	0.667	0.856	1	0.896	0.848	0.828
2020	0.617	0.797	0.896	1	0.921	0.897
2021	0.586	0.758	0.848	0.921	1	0.958
2022	0.575	0.742	0.828	0.897	0.958	1

Table 4: Kendall rank correlations for citation impact values ECI (upper table) and citation counts OCC (lower table). Tables show that correlation coefficients are mainly higher (10 out of 15) for ECI than for OCC, especially when time interval between rankings is longer. I.e., ECI based correlations are more stable as well.

123 In order to still illustrate the source of differences in the rankings, influence of
124 second step citations to the impact indicator is visualized in Figure 5. There two
125 publications with equal amounts of direct citations but different local graphs are
126 compared.

127 As a one more test in this study, the method was applied to a small set of hybrid
128 open access articles, part of which were known to be published under a so called
129 transformative agreement. This test was done to get information about the type
130 of articles that researchers publish taking advantage of these agreements. The 133
131 articles were published 2018-2020 in five journals, most publishing environmental
132 sciences, and their citation impact values indicate that the transformatives did not
133 have a clear impact advantage but were somewhat more frequent in the top half
134 than their share of the total set would suggest. The idea is also to follow how the
135 result changes for this set, having multiple publication years and two funding type
136 classes.

(a) Local citation graph of a publication in the UH set: ECI for this graph is **1.878**, which is calculated using the shown two citation step graph and $k(cc_2) = 1.248$ ($cc_2 = 11$).

(b) Local citation graph of a publication in the UH set: ECI for this graph is **2.259**, which is calculated using the shown two citation step graph and $k(cc_2) = 1.488$ ($cc_2 = 130$).

Figure 5: Two graphs representing the same direct citation count $cc_0 = 8$, but different second citation step count cc_1 (13 and 43). The citation impact indicator developed in this work takes into account second and third step citations in a way that significantly influences the estimates.

137 4 Conclusions

138 An approach to estimate citation impact while no using research field classifications
139 has been described here. This method uses the first two citation steps upstream from
140 a publication to characterize the width of information spread and the third step to
141 model the connection to the rest of the citation network. The presented citation
142 impact indicator ECI predicts future impact in a stable way. Meaning of the actual
143 calculated correlation and mutual information MI values between rankings after
144 varying time intervals was not studied here, though the rank correlations were high
145 and the dependence measure MI values seemed significant.

146 If needed, components of the impact measure can be modified, i.e., normalization
147 can be based on a different distribution and the functional form for the connection
148 between local graph and rest of the network can be changed. The method can also
149 likely be helped with machine learning techniques like natural language processing,
150 e.g., to characterize citation contexts for determining impact weights for the units.
151 These would correspond to the strength of the reason to cite, which connects the
152 unit internally. Also, a publication can be cited in another publication multiple
153 times with varying reasons, modeling of which would require enhancing the present
154 method at least through the graph structure. This extension can likely be in the form
155 of multigraphs with weighted edges allowed. Models incorporating more than two
156 citation steps in the local graph could of course be studied and their results would
157 likely be harder to interpret. Finally, to estimate more generic than citation impact,
158 links based on other information besides reference lists, naturally one possibility is
159 the text itself, could be added to a local graph.

160 One central goal of this work has been to avoid using any form of research field
161 classifications. The method here is focused on the studied individual publication
162 and the strength with which it has so far been able to spread information into
163 scientific literature. It is considered to demonstrate that new meaningful ways to
164 define citation impact without relying on research field classifications can be found.

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